

Soft-sensor for Estimating Ozone concentration

A rapport on soft-sensor Development from the activity A4.4.9.

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1 Activities Description

The report includes the activities and outputs from the activity A.4.4.9 described in the project protocol as followed;

“Drawing on data metrics in A1.2.1, uncertainty-aware sensor fusion methods in A1.3.3 and assessment of aspects of sensor networks in A2.1.2 (performed in parallel), UH with the assistance of VINS and VTT will enhance metrological aspects in developing soft sensors based on the hierarchical air quality monitoring network of e.g., UH and/or AIRPARIF.”

2 Background and Context

Atmospheric pollution has become a global problem because of its catastrophic effects on ecosystems as well as human health (Pan et al., 2023a). Specifically, since the beginning of the 21st century, increased levels of trace gases resulting from intensified emissions have enhanced the adverse effects on the environment. Ozone (O_3), out of all the trace gases, is a highly reactive and oxidative compound gas that is formed in the lower atmosphere by the photochemistry of other trace gases by solar radiation. Owing to its highly reactive chemical properties, it is very harmful for human health, vegetation, building materials, and other ecosystems. It is estimated that in exposure to ozone pollution contributed to 365,222 deaths globally in 2019, which accounted for 0.65% of global deaths (Hu & Yang, 2024).

Measuring ozone (O_3) concentrations in the environment is vital for shaping environmental policy and regulatory agencies such as the WHO (World Health Organization) and EPA (United States Environmental Protection Agency), which use data from ozone monitoring to establish thresholds (e.g., 8- hour average ozone levels) (Hilly et al., 2024). Efforts to measure ozone (O_3) include fixed ground-based monitoring networks, equipped with analyzers measuring ozone (O_3) concentrations in real time, using the UV photometry methods. Global ozone observations including those in the troposphere and stratosphere, are provided by satellite devices such as TROPOMI and OMI (Ozone Monitoring Instrument) (Levelt et al., 2006), and recently, the advancement in the use of Low Cost Sensors (LCS) has made it easier to measure ozone (O_3) concentrations in areas where ground monitoring stations or satellites are not providing permanent and continuous monitoring (Castell et al., 2017).

Despite all these efforts, reliable and abundant data is not available for ozone (O_3) measurements worldwide. The primary reason for this is that accurately measuring ozone (O_3) concentrations frequently comes at a high expense since it requires

sophisticated infrastructure, equipment, and knowledge. These expenses may prevent extensive monitoring, especially in environments with limited resources. Commonly used instruments include Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrometers, chemiluminescent analyzers, and UV photometers and although these instruments offer accurate measurements of ozone (O_3), they are costly to buy and operate (Buehler et al., 2021). On the other hand, although new low-cost ozone sensors have shown potential for wider use, their accuracy and dependability remain limited. The results provided by them are often inaccurate and unreliable, hindering the widespread use of low-cost sensors (LCS). Moreover, ensuring their accuracy is complicated by the fact that the calibration process itself is tedious and resource-intensive (Castell et al., 2017).

Previously, several predictive models for ozone concentration have been developed. For instance, (Alghamdi et al., 2019) proposed separate models for daytime and night-time ozone concentrations using data collected from a coastal monitoring site in Jeddah. Similarly, (Zaidan et al., 2019) introduced a pollutant proxy model for estimating ozone concentrations, which can also be generalized to other atmospheric pollutants. However, a key limitation of these existing models is their location-specific performance—a model that performs well at one site may not exhibit similar accuracy in other environments (Zhou et al., 2023). Consequently, there remains a continued need to retrain and adapt models for different geographical locations. In addition, some models rely on complex or less accessible input variables, which are not consistently available across all monitoring networks. (Pan et al., 2023b)

In this study, we address these limitations by developing soft sensors for ozone estimation using data obtained from the SMEAR III station in Kumpula, Helsinki—a state-of-the-art environmental monitoring facility. The proposed approach utilizes simple and readily available environmental and meteorological variables, ensuring the broader applicability of the developed models across various monitoring contexts.

3 Materials and Data Sources

Station for Measuring Ecosystem-Atmosphere Relations (SMEAR III) (Figure 1) is a station to measure the relationship between atmosphere and forest in Boreal climate zone for research and scientific exploration [Kulmala, 2018]. It is located at Kumpula campus University of Helsinki in front of the open yard, almost 4 km north-east from the Helsinki center. SMEAR III is situated 26 meters above sea level on a Rocky hill. This sub-urban air quality monitoring site features diverse surface types, including built structures, parking areas, roads, and vegetation. Located

approximately 150 meters from a main street in the Kumpula district of Helsinki, SMEAR III is equipped with an array of instruments. These include trace-level gas-phase pollutant sensors and Eddy covariance systems installed at a 31-meter height. The station, along with its gas and aerosol sensors, provides valuable data on air pollutant fluxes. Figure 1 shows the location of the SMEAR III station in Kumpula, Helsinki, denoted by a blue dot on the map.

Figure 1: SMEAR III Monitoring Station in Kumpula, Helsinki, Finland

The SmartSMEAR platform provides continuous atmospheric and meteorological observations from the SMEAR stations operated by the Institute for Atmospheric and Earth System Research (INAR), University of Helsinki. For this work, we obtained data from the SMEAR-III supersite, measured by the following sensors as seen in table 1.

Sensor type	Measured Parameter(s)	Unit
Pt100	Temperature (T)	°C
HMP155	Relative Humidity (RH)	%RH
Vaisala DPA502	Pressure (P)	hPa
Tapered Element Oscillating Microbalance (TEOM 1405-D)	Particulate Matter (PM)	µg/m ³

Chemiluminescence Analyzer (Thermo TEI42S)	Nitric Oxide (NO), Nitrogen Dioxide (NO ₂)	ppb
UV Photometric Analyzer (TEI49)	Ozone (O ₃)	ppb
IR Absorption Analyzer (Horiba APMA-370)	Carbon Monoxide (CO)	ppb

Table 1: Sensor types used in the SMEAR station

Hourly data spanning 1 August 2019, 00:00 UTC, to 31 December 2022, 23:59 UTC, were obtained from the SmartSMEAR database (<https://smear.avaa.csc.fi>). Finland uses Eastern European Time (EET) (UTC+02:00) in the winter and Eastern European Summer Time (EEST) (UTC+03:00) during the summer. For the purpose of soft-sensor development, the dataset was preprocessed to ensure data quality and consistency; all records containing missing values were removed prior to analysis.

4 Soft sensor development

4.1 Methodology

A softsensor (also called a *virtual sensor* or *software sensor*) is a computational model that estimates a variable that's hard to measure directly, using data from other easier-to-measure variables (Perera et al., 2023). In other words, instead of relying on an expensive or unavailable physical sensor, a soft sensor *infers* the needed value from correlated signals.

Developing softsensors typically involve several technical steps, including:

1. Data collection – for this study, hourly data from the SMEAR III station were utilized.
2. Feature selection – identifying the variables most strongly correlated with the target variable; this process is described in detail later in the report.
3. Modeling – applying machine learning algorithms to learn the relationships between input variables and the target.
4. Validation – evaluating the soft sensor's performance by comparing the estimated values with actual measurements to assess model accuracy.

4.2 Feature Selection

In soft-sensor development, feature selection is a critical preprocessing step that involves identifying and selecting the most relevant input variables (features) that significantly contribute to predicting the target variable. This process aims to enhance model accuracy, interpretability, and computational efficiency by eliminating redundant or irrelevant features. (Cai et al., 2018).

For this task, feature selection was carried out to identify the most relevant input variables that contribute significantly to the prediction of the target variable in the soft-sensor model. The objective of this step was to enhance model performance, reduce overfitting, and improve interpretability by eliminating redundant or weakly correlated variables.

Initially, a correlation analysis was performed to examine the relationships between all measured variables and the target parameter. The Pearson correlation coefficient was used to quantify linear dependencies, while scatter plots and pairwise relationships were inspected visually to detect potential nonlinear trends. Variables showing very weak or inconsistent correlations were excluded from further analysis.

The final results can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Correlation Matrix of Atmospheric Variables in SMEAR III

Figure 2 represents the correlation matrix, illustrating the degree of linear association among the atmospheric variables at the Kumpula (K) station. In the matrix, a maroon colour indicates a strong positive correlation ($r = 1.00$), signifying that both variables increase or decrease together, whereas a blue colour denotes a strong negative correlation ($r = -1.00$), implying that as one variable increases, the other tends to decrease. Colours approaching white correspond to weak or

negligible correlations ($r \approx 0$), suggesting little or no linear relationship between the respective variables.

The analysis reveals that relative humidity (RH) exhibits the strongest negative correlation with ozone (O_3) ($r = -0.49$), followed by nitrogen oxides (NO_x) ($r = -0.44$), carbon monoxide (CO) ($r = -0.38$), and nitric oxide (NO) ($r = -0.28$). These negative associations reflect typical urban photochemical dynamics, where elevated concentrations of primary pollutants such as NO and CO promote ozone titration and thus lower ambient O_3 levels. (Song et al., 2024)

Conversely, O_3 shows positive correlations with global radiation (GR) ($r = 0.35$), wind speed (WS) ($r = 0.29$), and temperature (T) ($r = 0.26$). These relationships indicate that favorable meteorological conditions, including higher solar radiation and temperature, enhance photochemical ozone formation, while increased wind speed supports pollutant dispersion and atmospheric mixing. The observed correlations align with established findings in urban air quality studies, where ozone variability is strongly modulated by both photochemical activity and meteorological drivers. (Bu et al., 2020).

Based on these results, the following atmospheric variables were selected to be used as features in the soft sensor:

1. Relative Humidity (RH).
2. Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x).
3. Carbon Monoxide (CO).
4. Global Radiation (R).
5. Wind Speed (WS).
6. Nitrogen Monoxide (NO).
7. Temperature (T).
8. Particulate Matter 2.5 micrometers or smaller ($PM_{2.5}$).

4.3 Modeling and Validation

To identify the most suitable predictive model for soft-sensor development, a comprehensive evaluation of various machine learning algorithms was performed. The objective of testing multiple models was to capture different types of relationships between the selected input variables and the target variable, thereby ensuring both robustness and accuracy in the final soft-sensor.

4.3.1 Linear and Regularized Models

The first group of models consisted of Linear Regression, Partial Least Squares (PLS) Regression, and Lasso Regression. (James et al., 2021).

- **Linear Regression** assumes a linear relationship between predictors and the target variable, offering interpretability and simplicity.
- **PLS Regression** (Partial Least Squares) is a dimensionality reduction technique that projects predictors into a new space, maximizing the covariance between predictors and the target. This makes it suitable for datasets with multicollinearity or a high number of correlated variables.
- **Lasso Regression** (Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator) introduces a regularization term that penalizes large coefficients, effectively performing feature selection by shrinking less important variable coefficients toward zero. This helps reduce overfitting and improves model generalization.

4.3.2 Support Vector Regression (SVR)

Several variants of Support Vector Regression (SVR) were tested, including linear, polynomial, radial basis function (RBF), and sigmoid kernels. SVR aims to find a function that approximates the target variable with minimal error, while maintaining a margin of tolerance (ϵ) around the predicted values. By transforming the input space through kernel functions, SVR can model nonlinear relationships—a desirable property when dealing with complex atmospheric or sensor data. (Smola et al., 2004)

4.3.3 Neural Network-Based Models

Two variants of Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) models were implemented to capture highly nonlinear dependencies among variables. MLPs are feedforward artificial neural networks composed of multiple layers of interconnected neurons that learn data representations through iterative optimization. (Bickel et al., n.d.).

- The first MLP configuration used default hyperparameters.
- The second (MLP-II) employed a grid search optimization procedure to fine-tune hyperparameters such as the number of hidden layers, neurons per layer, learning rate, and activation functions, thus improving predictive performance.

4.3.4 Tree-Based Ensemble Models

A diverse set of ensemble learning algorithms was also examined, including Random Forest, Bagging, Gradient Boosting (GBoost), Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost), Histogram Gradient Boosting (HistGBoost), and Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM). These models combine multiple weak learners—typically decision trees—to produce a stronger predictive model. (Bickel et al., n.d.).

- **Random Forest** and **Bagging** improve stability and reduce variance through averaging over many trees.
- **Boosting methods** (e.g., GBoost, AdaBoost, HistGBoost, LightGBM) iteratively focus on correcting errors made by previous models, achieving higher accuracy and robustness.
- **LightGBM**, a modern gradient boosting framework, is optimized for speed and efficiency with large datasets, making it particularly effective for environmental and sensor-based regression tasks.

Table 2: List of Machine Learning Models compared for selecting optimal performing model

No.	Model	Type / Category	Key Advantages and Characteristics
1	Linear Regression	Linear	Serves as a baseline model; provides interpretability and measures linear relationships between predictors and the target variable.
2	Partial Least Squares (PLS) Regression	Linear / Latent-Variable	Handles multicollinearity and high-dimensional data by projecting predictors into latent components that maximize covariance with the response.
3	Lasso Regression	Linear / Regularized	Applies an ℓ_1 penalty to perform variable selection and reduce overfitting by shrinking less significant coefficients toward zero.
4	Support Vector Regression (SVR) – Linear	Nonlinear (Kernel-based)	Captures linear relationships with controlled complexity using an ϵ -insensitive loss function.
5	Support Vector Regression (SVR) – Polynomial	Nonlinear (Kernel-based)	Models polynomial relationships among variables through kernel transformations.
6	Support Vector Regression (SVR) – Radial Basis Function (RBF)	Nonlinear (Kernel-based)	Efficiently captures complex nonlinear interactions by mapping input data into higher-dimensional feature space.
7	Support Vector Regression (SVR) – Sigmoid	Nonlinear (Kernel-based)	Employs a sigmoid kernel to represent relationships similar to neural activation functions.
8	Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) – I	Neural Network	Captures highly nonlinear dependencies between variables; flexible and data-driven.
9	Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) – II (Grid Search)	Neural Network (Optimized)	Same as above, but with hyperparameter optimization (via grid search) to improve predictive performance.
10	Random Forest	Ensemble (Bagging)	Combines multiple decision trees to reduce variance and enhance generalization; robust to outliers and noise.
11	Bagging Regressor	Ensemble (Bagging)	Reduces variance and overfitting by averaging predictions from multiple base estimators trained on bootstrap samples.
12	Gradient Boosting (GBoost)	Ensemble (Boosting)	Sequentially fits weak learners to residuals to improve accuracy; effective for structured, tabular data.
13	Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost)	Ensemble (Boosting)	Adjusts model weights iteratively to emphasize difficult-to-predict observations.
14	Histogram-Based Gradient Boosting (HistGBoost)	Ensemble (Boosting)	A computationally efficient variant of gradient boosting suitable for large datasets.

15	Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM)	Ensemble (Boosting)	Fast and efficient gradient boosting framework; handles large-scale, high-dimensional data with improved memory efficiency.
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4.3.4 Model Comparison and Selection

The modelling process was designed to systematically evaluate the performance of all the above listed machine learning algorithms for soft-sensor development. The models were trained and validated using different combinations of the selected input variables to determine the most effective feature set for accurate prediction of the target parameter. In total, 256 combinations of variables were generated and tested for each model to comprehensively explore the influence of variable selection on predictive performance.

Each model was trained on the same dataset split into training and testing subsets, typically following a 70:30 ratio, ensuring consistent comparison across algorithms. Model hyperparameters were optimized using grid search or built-in tuning procedures, depending on the algorithm, to achieve the best balance between bias and variance.

Performance evaluation was carried out using standard statistical metrics, including the coefficient of determination (R^2), mean square error (MSE), root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE) and median absolute percentage error (MAPE). These metrics provided quantitative measures of model accuracy, stability, and generalization capability. The final soft-sensor model was selected based on its ability to deliver high predictive accuracy with consistent performance across validation folds and variable combinations.

Figure 3 shows the feature combination matrix used to run all possible features for all selected models.

Figure 3: Feature Combination Matrix

5 Results

The results of the soft-sensor modelling are summarized in **Table 3**, which presents the best-performing configuration for each tested algorithm, along with their corresponding performance metrics for ozone (O₃) prediction. Each model was trained and evaluated using the optimal combination of atmospheric variables identified during the feature selection process, primarily including NO_x, CO, PM_{2.5}, relative humidity (RH), temperature (T), global radiation (R), and wind speed (WS).

Overall, the results demonstrate noticeable differences in predictive capability across the various modelling approaches. Linear models, such as *Linear Regression* ($R^2 = 0.472$, $RMSE = 6.93$), *PLS Regression* ($R^2 = 0.467$, $RMSE = 6.89$), and *Lasso Regression* ($R^2 = 0.469$, $RMSE = 7.03$), provided a baseline level of performance. These relatively modest R^2 values and comparatively high errors indicate that while some degree of linear correlation exists between the selected predictors and O₃ concentrations, the underlying atmospheric processes are not purely linear.

In contrast, nonlinear approaches achieved substantially better predictive accuracy. Among the Support Vector Regression (SVR) variants, the Radial Basis Function (RBF) and Polynomial kernels both achieved an R^2 of 0.485 and RMSE of 6.84, outperforming their linear and sigmoid counterparts. This improvement suggests that nonlinear kernel transformations better capture the complex dependencies between ozone and its precursor gases (NO_x, CO) as well as meteorological drivers (T, RH, R).

The neural network-based models also exhibited strong predictive capability. The *MLP-I* configuration achieved an R^2 of 0.610 with an RMSE of 5.89, while the *MLP-II (Grid Search)* further improved performance to an R^2 of 0.703 and RMSE of 5.14, representing a notable enhancement in predictive accuracy following hyperparameter optimization. These results confirm the effectiveness of data-driven neural architectures in modelling the nonlinear and interactive relationships inherent in atmospheric processes.

The tree-based ensemble models demonstrated the highest overall performance. *Random Forest* achieved the best results with an R^2 of **0.770**, $RMSE = 4.53$, $MAE = 3.38$, and $MAPE = 9.94\%$, indicating a high degree of predictive reliability and generalization. This was closely followed by Bagging ($R^2 = 0.769$, $RMSE = 4.53$) and Histogram Gradient Boosting ($R^2 = 0.721$, $RMSE = 4.98$), while LightGBM also performed competitively ($R^2 = 0.725$, $RMSE = 4.95$). This indicates that ensemble-based algorithms are particularly well suited to heterogeneous atmospheric data, as they effectively reduce variance through averaging and capture complex interactions through hierarchical partitioning.

Among all models, Random Forest emerged as the most effective soft-sensor configuration for real-time O₃ estimation, combining the lowest RMSE and MAPE values with the **highest coefficient of determination (R² = 0.770)**. This indicates that the model was able to reproduce observed ozone concentrations with high accuracy and stability.

Table 3 : Performance metrics from all models with the best performing features

Model	Selected Features	R ²	MSE	RMSE	MAE	MAPE (%)
Linear Regression	NO _x , CO, PM _{2.5} , RH, T, R, WS	0.472	47.98	6.93	5.52	17.85
PLS Regression	NO _x , CO, PM _{2.5} , RH, T, R, WS	0.467	47.40	6.89	5.54	18.29
Lasso Regression	NO _x , CO, PM _{2.5} , RH, T, R, WS	0.469	49.40	7.03	5.63	17.71
SVR (Linear)	NO _x , CO, PM _{2.5} , RH, T, R, WS	0.444	50.44	7.10	5.49	17.45
SVR (Polynomial)	NO _x , PM _{2.5} , RH, T, R, WS	0.485	46.76	6.84	5.43	17.15
SVR (Radial)	NO _x , PM _{2.5} , RH, T, R, WS	0.485	46.76	6.84	5.43	17.15
SVR (Sigmoid)	RH	-0.130	102.50	10.12	7.95	23.32
MLP-I	NO _x , CO, PM _{2.5} , RH, T, R, WS	0.610	34.69	5.89	4.65	15.30
MLP-II (Grid Search)	NO _x , CO, PM _{2.5} , RH, T, R, WS	0.703	26.38	5.14	3.96	12.75
Random Forest	NO _x , CO, PM _{2.5} , RH, T, R, WS	0.770	20.48	4.53	3.38	9.94
Bagging	NO _x , CO, PM _{2.5} , RH, T, R, WS	0.769	20.51	4.53	3.38	10.03
Gradient Boosting (GBoost)	NO _x , CO, PM _{2.5} , RH, T, R, WS	0.636	32.41	5.69	4.53	14.93
AdaBoost	NO _x , CO, PM _{2.5} , RH, T, R, WS	0.474	46.77	6.84	5.55	17.73
Histogram Gradient Boosting (HistGBoost)	NO _x , CO, PM _{2.5} , RH, T, R, WS	0.721	24.81	4.98	3.84	12.20
Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM)	NO _x , CO, PM _{2.5} , RH, T, R, WS	0.725	24.49	4.95	3.83	11.89

6 Conclusion

The comparative analysis of machine learning models for ozone prediction in Kumpula, Helsinki revealed that the Random Forest algorithm exhibited the most robust performance. Utilizing a combination of nitrogen oxides (NO_x), carbon monoxide (CO), particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), relative humidity (RH), temperature, global reflected radiation, and wind speed as Predictor variables, Random Forest achieved the highest coefficient of determination (R² = 0.770). This indicates a strong Capability to Capture the complex, nonlinear interactions among the selected atmospheric parameters influencing ozone concentrations. The Bagging (R² = 0.796) and Histogram-based Gradient Boosting (R² = 0.721) models also demonstrated competitive performance, underscoring the effectiveness of ensemble learning methods in atmospheric data modeling. Overall, the findings suggest that ensemble-based approaches, particularly Random Forest, provide

a reliable framework for improving the accuracy of air quality prediction in urban environments.

This study confirms that ensemble learning methods, particularly Random Forest, are highly effective for modeling ozone concentrations in complex atmospheric environments. The integration of pollutant and meteorological predictors enables a more comprehensive understanding of ozone formation mechanisms, thereby supporting the advancement of Intelligent environmental monitoring systems.

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